

Skills 4 eosc

D1.2 Data Management Plan - intermediate update

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable is the second version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Skills4EOSC project, delivered in M18. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the Embedding Open Science in the Skills4EOSC Methodology section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosC-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and used, and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the Horizon Europe DMP template.

Emma Lazzeri (GARR) acts as the data manager in the Skills4EOSC project and is in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

The Skills4EOSC project has implemented various strategies to align with Open Science and FAIR principles. These strategies are reflected in the DMP and in the Skills4EOSC Starter Kit, a reference document on project management procedures that is available to all project participants.

1.2 Data summary

Table 1 presents an overview of datasets that we create within the project. It is based on the analysis of outputs of all work packages. We will collect the survey data using online tools. Specific tools will be determined later, and the DMP will be updated to reflect it. A subset of data that will be made available at the end of the project may be relevant to everyone interested in EOSC and its activities. We do not reuse any data in this project.

Table 1 - Produced datasets.

<i>dataset ID</i>	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
<i>P1</i>	Deliverables and reports	Standard office documents	PDF	100 MB	no

<i>P2</i>	General survey among the Skills4EOSC partners	Standard office document, Structured text	PDF, CSV	100 MB	yes
<i>P3</i>	Survey among the PhD students from the Skills4EOSC partners	Standard office documents, Structured text	PDF, CSV	100 MB	yes
<i>P4</i>	Administrative data for the project	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	yes
<i>P5</i>	Registry of RDM training resources	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
<i>P6</i>	List of reference sources for minimum viable skillset properties	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
<i>P7</i>	OSCC Incubator Programme video recordings	Audio-visual data	MP4	5 GB	yes
<i>P8</i>	Events video recordings	Audio-visual data	MP4	5 GB	no
<i>P9</i>	Reviews from training participants (questions, tests, answers...)	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
<i>P10</i>	Participants information	Standard office documents	CSV	100 MB	yes
<i>P11</i>	Participating institutions information	Standard office documents	CSV	100 MB	yes
<i>P12</i>	Presentations given for the project	Standard office documents	PDF	100 MG	no

Several tasks and activities in the project require the gathering and classification of existing materials and resources that are not produced by the project but serve as sources for the work of Skills4EOSC members. These

important resources are shared in a systematic way through the Skills4EOSC related Zotero Libraries and made available to the larger EOSC and Open Science community.

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository (Zenodo) that provides a persistent identifier (DOI) and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

We will use the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)¹ metadata standards whenever possible to document survey data. In all other cases, we will provide a README file explaining of all values and terms used next to each file with data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the Zenodo repository, which is DataCite metadata².

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. For clear and persistent reference, we will provide the data creators' ORCID iDs in Zenodo.

2.2 Making data accessible

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. All the data that cannot be made open or needs to be deleted is described in Section 5.

We will use Zenodo to publish data. Zenodo is a simple and innovative trusted service that allows researchers, scientists, EU projects, and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based

¹ <https://ddialliance.org/>

² <https://schema.datacite.org>

repositories of the research communities. Zenodo enables researchers, scientists, EU projects, and institutions to:

- easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats, including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science.
- display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission.
- easily access and reuse shared research results.

All the project outputs can be found on the project community page³ that is maintained by the data manager.

The repository will host the data for at least 20 years, but a longer retention period is expected. This meets our requirements.

Table 2 provides an overview of datasets, their location and expected license used for publication.

Table 2 - Overview of datasets and repositories used for their publication, including a license.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
<i>P1</i>	Open		2025-08-30	Zenodo		CC BY 4.0
<i>P2</i>	Open	Must be anonymised before publication	2025-08-30	Zenodo		CC BY 4.0
<i>P3</i>	Open	Must be anonymised before publication	2025-08-30	Zenodo		CC BY 4.0
<i>P5</i>	Open		2025-08-30	Zenodo		CC BY

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/skills4eosc/>

					4.0
<i>P6</i>	Open		2025-08-30	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0
<i>P8</i>	Open		2025-08-30	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0
<i>P9</i>	Open		2025-08-30	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0
<i>P12</i>	Open		2025-08-30	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0

Milestones in the project are treated as short reports. They are included in P1 and published as soon as they are available. In Zenodo, the reports are specified as “Project milestones”.

Milestone reports and public deliverables are reviewed by project partners who were not involved in creating the documents and approved by the coordinator before publication. A DOI is reserved in Zenodo and placed on the front page of the document prior to the upload. As a measure to support co-creation and enhance reproducibility, public milestones and deliverables are published as soon as possible, even in draft versions. Updated documents are later added as new versions to the existing records, followed by final versions at the end of the project.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Whenever possible, we follow standards such as DDI or DataCite to foster interoperability of data. As far as possible, we use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We ensure good documentation of our datasets and provide README files in addition to a clear description in Zenodo wherever needed to inform about methods used for collecting or generating the data, data specific parameters, etc.

2.4 Increase data re-use

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata to all published datasets and comprehensive README files where needed. The descriptions and documentation associated with the project results will include details on the methodology used and analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there are no data protection concerns (see Table 2).

We use consistent and meaningful file names that reflect the file content and file formats that are recommended for long-term preservation.

3 Other research outputs

One of the project's key outputs is learning materials produced by WP3-6 targeting different stakeholders. The design of Skills4EOSC materials is based on the core deliverable D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials⁴. The methodology is a result of task 2.3, which passed a co-design process engaging the Skills4EOSC participants and the larger EOSC community via specific a consultation mechanism. It was published in Zenodo in M12.

The methodology includes specification for metadata schema and repositories to be used, processes to ensure the material is in line with the FAIR principles, and thus fully reusable by both trainers and trainees, as well as a mechanism to assess the quality of the material itself.

⁴ Filiposka, S., Green, D., Mishev, A., Kjorveziroski, V., Corleto, A., Napolitano, E., Paolini, G., Di Giorgio, S., Janik, J., Schirru, L., Gingold, A., Hadrossek, C., Souyioultzoglou, I., Leister, C., Pavone, G., Sharma, S., Mendez Rodriguez, E. M., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305540>

4 Allocation of resources

The data manager directs the data management process overall, with the work package leaders being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up, and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

The costs of data management are all staff costs and accounted for.

5 Data security

For the duration of the project, the data manager ensures safe storage and backup of data. During the project, data will be stored in **workplace.skills4eosc.eu** with limited access to people involved in the given WP. The service is hosted in Italy by GARR. It is GDPR compliant, and the data is backed-up.

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. In this project, there will be sensitive data in datasets P2 (General survey among the Skills4EOSC partners), P3 (Survey among the PhD students from the Skills4EOSC partners), P4 (Administrative data for the project), P7 (OSCC Incubator Programme video recordings), P10 (Participants information) and P11 (Participating institutions information). To ensure that the storage and transfer of sensitive data is safe, additional security measures such as individual log-in and password are taken. Selected work package members will be authorised to access sensitive data.

In this project, we will process personal data (see section 1.2). P2 (General survey among the Skills4EOSC partners), P3 (Survey among the PhD students from the Skills4EOSC partners), P4 (Administrative data for the project), P7 (OSCC Incubator Programme video recordings), P10 (Participants information) and P11 (Participating institutions information) will contain personal data. To ensure compliance with data protection laws, gaining informed consent for processing personal data and pseudonymisation of personal data will be used.

Table 3 - Access control rights for datasets during the project.

<i>dataset ID</i>	selected project members	all other project members	the public
<i>P1</i>	writing	writing	no access
<i>P2</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P3</i>	writing	no access	no access

<i>P4</i>	writing	no access	no access
<i>P5</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P6</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P7</i>	writing	no access	no access
<i>P8</i>	writing	no access	no access
<i>P9</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P10</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P11</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P12</i>	writing	reading only	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

Not all of the datasets can be published at the end of the project. Table 4 lists datasets that must be deleted.

Table 4 - Datasets to be deleted.

<i>kind/name of data</i>	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person
<i>P3</i>	2025-08-30	Includes sensitive or personal data that cannot be made public.	Data Manager
<i>P7</i>	2025-08-30	Includes sensitive or personal data that cannot be made public.	Data Manager
<i>P10</i>	2025-08-30	Includes sensitive or personal data that cannot be made public.	Data Manager
<i>P11</i>	2025-08-30	Includes sensitive or	Data

		personal data that cannot be made public.	Manager
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Datasets P2 and P4 contain sensitive and personal data. They will not be deleted but moved at the end of the project to suitable storage operated by the EOSC Association.

6 ELSI

Skills4EOSC takes into account the Ethical, Legal and Social Issues in the project activities in its ELSI meta work package, which is transversal in the methodology. As ELSI are embedded throughout the activities of all work packages as transversal elements, one task from the ELSI Meta-WP is included in all relevant work packages (WP2. 3.4 and 5).

In the period covered by this DMP version, the ELSI related project activities included discussion on the following aspects:

- Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)
- Public Sector Information (PSI),
- Open Data,
- licensing,
- database rights,
- integrity,
- responsible and participatory research,
- impact on society

In particular the ELSI aspects are discussed in WP3 to cover the science for policy interface and in WP5, addressing the different needs of the various research communities and the accessibility of the various types of data they produce.

These discussions address the balance between sharing research results under the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” and the ethical impact on involved communities and individuals, as well as the legal aspects deriving from mandates and regulations, policies and legislative interventions at all levels.

7 Other issues

None. This section will be updated if issues arise.

8 References

No	Description/Link
R1	European Commission (2021). Horizon Europe (HORIZON) - Annotated Model Grant Agreement. Version 0.2, 30 November 2021. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf
R2	European Commission (2022a). Horizon Europe (HORIZON) - Model Grant Agreement. Version 1.1., 15 April 2022. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/agr-contr/general-mga_horizon-euratom_en.pdf